

Solubility Product of Hg_2SO_4 at a Number of Temperatures

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Solubility product of Hg_2SO_4 , i.e., $a_{\text{Hg}_2} \times a_{\text{SO}_4}$ at 25° was determined by Brodsky¹ and was found to be 4.7×10^{-7} . At other temperatures it is not known. We required the values at other temperatures also in connection with the study of the cell;

Hence this investigation was done.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mercurous sulphate was prepared by the electrolytic method². The paste of mercurous sulphate, rinsed a number of times with 0.001 *M* sulphuric acid, was taken in a dry conical flask to which about 300 ml of 0.001 *M* H_2SO_4 was added. This mixture was stirred with a magnetic stirrer in thermostat whose temperature was controlled within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The solution was filtered in the thermostat itself through a glass (G_3) sintered funnel. 50 ml. of the filtrate was mixed with 5 ml. of CCl_4 , concentrated hydrochloric acid and some sodium carbonate (to provide CO_2 —gas atmosphere during titration) to make the solution 3–4 *N* with respect to hydrochloric acid after the neutralisation of Na_2CO_3 . The mixture was heated to 50 – 60° and titrated with 0.0033445 *M* KIO_3 from a calibrated microburette till the violet colour disappeared. The results of duplicate were the same. Heating is necessary for completing the reaction at low concentration used in these experiments. This modified procedure was checked by estimating the corresponding amount of mercurous chloride. The solution, stirred for 3 hr. gave the same results as solution, stirred for 5 hr. but stirring was done for 5 hr. in every case to be on the safe side.

TABLE

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	CC. (of sat. solution of Hg_2SO_4 in 0.001 <i>M</i> H_2SO_4) taken	CC. of 0.0033445 <i>M</i> KIO_3 required	gm. moles/ litre $[\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4] \times 10^4$ $= [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \times 10^4$	gm. moles/ litre $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$	$\text{Ksp} \times 10^7$
15	50	6.14	8.22	1.68	6.00	7.42
25	50	6.76	9.04	1.70	6.21	8.08
35	50	7.37	9.86	1.73	6.43	8.73

DISCUSSION

It has been shown that $\log K_A$, i.e.,

$$\log \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]} = \log K + 4A \sqrt{\mu} - \beta \mu \quad \dots (1)$$

1. A. E. Brodsky, *Ztscher. Elektrochem.*, 1929, 35, 883.
2. G. A. Hulett, *Phys. Rev.*, 1911, 32, 257.

The value of K , A and β for various temperatures have been given in an earlier paper³. In a saturated solution of Hg_2SO_4 in dilute sulphuric acid, if α is the degree of dissociation of HSO_4^- and C_1 and C_2 are stoichiometric concentration of H_2SO_4 and Hg_2SO_4 then

$$K_A = \frac{(1+\alpha)(\alpha C_1 + C_2)}{(1-\alpha)} \quad \dots (2)$$

Now an arbitrary value assigned to μ and K_A is found from equation (1) and α from equation (2). A new value of ionic strength is calculated from :

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2}[H^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HSO}_4^-] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] = \frac{1}{2}(1+\alpha)C_1 + \frac{1}{2}(1-\alpha)C_1 + 2(\alpha C_1 + C_2) + 2C_2.$$

The process is repeated till μ is constant to the fourth place of decimal. The value of α , corresponding to this value of μ , represents the correct value. The values of $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ thus calculated are given in the table. Now

$$\log \frac{f \text{SO}_4 \times f \text{H}}{f \text{HSO}_4} = -4A \sqrt{\mu} + \beta \mu.$$

where the value of β is the same as in equation (1). We are justified in assuming that $f \text{H} = f \text{HSO}_4$ because both H and HSO_4 ions are univalent. It follows that $\log f \text{SO}_4 = -4A \sqrt{\mu} + \beta \mu$, where β is known. It is assumed that $f \text{Hg}_2 = f \text{SO}_4$. So $\log K_{sp(A)} = \log [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}] = \log K_{sp} + 8A \sqrt{\mu} - 2\beta \mu$. The calculated K_{sp} is given in the table. It may be pointed out that our value of (K_{sp}) at 25° differs from Brodsky's value. Brodsky found $-\log f \text{Hg}_2 = \sqrt{2} \times 4A \sqrt{c}$ instead of $4A \sqrt{c}$. He used $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ which must have been highly hydrolysed. Hence, we are not surprised to get a different value from his. Values of $\log K_{sp}$ at 15°, 25° and 35° come to 7.42×10^{-7} , 8.08×10^{-7} and 8.73×10^{-7} respectively. These values plotted against $1/T$, gave a straight line. The heat of solution (ΔH) of $\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightarrow \text{Hg}_2^{2+} + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ calculated from the above plot, comes to 1293.6 or 1300 cal in round numbers. The variation of K_{sp} with temperature is given by log

$$K_{sp} = -5.1400 - \frac{284.2}{T}$$

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